

Supplemental Material for “Heat Diffusion Invariant”

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Note 1. Thermal diffusion time

Transient and passive heat conduction in uniform media is governed by

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-\kappa \nabla T) = 0, \quad (\text{S1})$$

where ρC is volumetric heat capacity, κ is thermal conductivity, T is temperature, and t is time. Without loss of generality, we discuss a 1D semi-infinite case and reduce Eq. (S1) to

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(-D \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) = 0, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $D = \kappa/\rho C$ is thermal diffusivity.

The boundary and initial conditions are

$$T(x = 0, t) = T_1, \quad (\text{S3a})$$

$$T(x = \infty, t) = T_2, \quad (\text{S3b})$$

$$T(x, t = 0) = T_2, \quad (\text{S3c})$$

where T_1 and T_2 are constants. The solution to Eq. (S2) is

$$T = T_2 + (T_1 - T_2) \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{x}{2\sqrt{Dt}} \right), \quad (\text{S4})$$

where erfc is the complementary error function.

Due to $\operatorname{erfc}(0) = 1$, it takes an infinite amount of time for the temperature at $x \neq 0$ to reach T_1 . We define that it takes a thermal diffusion time of t for the temperature at $x = L$ to change by a fixed ratio smaller than 1. If that ratio takes 0.15, i.e., $\operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{L}{2\sqrt{Dt}} \right) = 0.15$, we can define thermal diffusion time as $t \approx L^2/(4D)$. The proportional relation of $t \sim L^2/D$ is vital, and the specific coefficient does not matter. We thus set that ratio as about 0.48 to exactly define thermal diffusion time as

$$t = \frac{L^2}{D}, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where thermal diffusivity D is isotropic.

We further consider anisotropic thermal diffusivity $D_{ij} = \kappa_{ij}/\rho C$, where i and j are the components of the Cartesian coordinate system. Since thermal conductivity is anisotropic, the heat flux direction does not follow the temperature gradient direction. The heat flux component J_T along the temperature gradient direction \hat{e}_T is

$$J_T = \hat{e}_T \cdot J = e_i \kappa_{ij} |\partial_j T| = e_i \kappa_{ij} e_j |\nabla T| = \kappa |\nabla T|, \quad (S6)$$

where the Einstein summation rule is utilized, J is heat flux, e_i and e_j are the components of \hat{e}_T , $\partial_j T$ is the component of the temperature gradient ∇T , and κ is the effective thermal conductivity along the temperature gradient direction \hat{e}_T . Based on Eq. (S6), we can obtain

$$\kappa = e_i \kappa_{ij} e_j. \quad (S7)$$

The effective thermal diffusivity D along the temperature gradient direction \hat{e}_T is

$$D = \frac{e_i \kappa_{ij} e_j}{\rho C} = e_i D_{ij} e_j. \quad (S8)$$

The anisotropic version of Eq. (S5) is

$$t = \frac{L^2}{e_i D_{ij} e_j}. \quad (S9)$$

Matching thermal diffusion time $t' = t$, or equivalently $\frac{L'^2}{e'_i D'_{ij} e'_j} = \frac{L^2}{e_i D_{ij} e_j}$, yields

$$|\nabla T'|^2 e'_i D'_{ij} e'_j = |\nabla T|^2 e_i D_{ij} e_j, \quad (S10)$$

where we have used the following relations,

$$L' = \frac{|\Delta T'|}{|\nabla T'|}, \quad (S11a)$$

$$L = \frac{|\Delta T|}{|\nabla T|}, \quad (S11b)$$

$$|\Delta T'| = |\Delta T|. \quad (S11c)$$

Equation (S10) can be rewritten as

$$(\partial_i T') D'_{ij} (\partial_j T') = (\partial_i T) D_{ij} (\partial_j T), \quad (S12)$$

which is the general definition of a heat diffusion invariant.

Note 2. Transformation thermotics

All transformation parameters predicted by transformation thermotics should satisfy the demand of Eq. (S12). The Jacobian transformation matrix is $B_{ij} = \partial x'_i / \partial x_j$, where x' and x are the coordinates in physical and virtual space. Transformation thermotics [1-3] predicts the following relations,

$$\partial_i T' = b_{ij} \partial_j T, \quad (\text{S13a})$$

$$\kappa'_{ij} = \frac{B_{iu} \kappa_{uv} B_{jv}}{\det B}, \quad (\text{S13b})$$

$$\rho' C' = \frac{\rho C}{\det B}, \quad (\text{S13c})$$

where b_{ij} is the inverse matrix of B_{ji} , satisfying $b_{ij} B_{kj} = \delta_{ik}$ (where δ_{ik} is the Kronecker symbol). With Eq. (S13), we have

$$(\partial_i T') D'_{ij} (\partial_j T') = (\partial_u T) b_{iu} \frac{\frac{B_{iu} \kappa_{uv} B_{jv}}{\det B}}{\frac{\rho C}{\det B}} b_{jv} (\partial_v T) = (\partial_u T) D_{uv} (\partial_v T), \quad (\text{S14})$$

which is equivalent to Eq. (S12). Hence, all transformation parameters should meet the demand of Eq. (S12). Note that the heat diffusion invariant does not need any coordinate transformation, which makes the heat diffusion invariant universal for other metamaterial design methods, such as scattering cancellation and inverse design.

Note 3. Analytical full parameters

We first present the general process of deriving full parameters. With known κ' , Eq. (S12) predicts $\rho' C' = (\partial_i T') \kappa'_{ij} (\partial_j T') / (DG^2)$. The isotropic version is $\rho' C' = \kappa' |\nabla T'|^2 / (DG^2)$. We can obtain T' by numerical simulation or analytically derive T' in regular geometries. If κ' is unknown, the conformality-assisted tracing approach works [4]. For the isotropic thermal diffusivity, Eq. (S12) predicts $D' = DG^2 / |\nabla T'|^2$. We can obtain $T' (= T^*)$ by setting $\kappa^* = \kappa$

in bottom Fig. 1(c). A streamline maps a bulk point with coordinates of (x_0, y_0) to a boundary point with a coordinate of y_1 . Tailoring thermal conductivity κ' along streamlines can achieve $J'_n = J_n$ without changing the temperature (i.e., $T' = T^*$) and mesh (i.e., $L' = L^*$). For proof, we denote the initial thermal conductivity as $\kappa^*(x, y)$. The corresponding temperature profile $T^*(x, y)$ satisfies $\nabla \cdot [\kappa^*(x, y) \cdot \nabla T^*(x, y)] = 0$. We consider a spatial distribution function $\varepsilon(x, y)$, expecting $\varepsilon(x, y)\kappa^*(x, y)$ to realize invisibility. Note that the isolines of $\varepsilon(x, y)$ are streamlines as we tailor thermal conductivity along streamlines, yielding $\nabla \varepsilon(x, y) \cdot J^* = 0$, with $J^* = -\kappa^*(x, y) \cdot \nabla T^*(x, y)$. We further consider the temperature profile $T'(x, y)$ with $\varepsilon(x, y)\kappa^*(x, y)$. The governing equation is $\nabla \cdot [\varepsilon(x, y)\kappa^*(x, y) \cdot \nabla T'(x, y)] = 0$, which can be written as $\nabla \varepsilon(x, y) \cdot [\kappa^*(x, y) \cdot \nabla T'(x, y)] + \varepsilon(x, y)\nabla \cdot [\kappa^*(x, y) \cdot \nabla T'(x, y)] = 0$. Use a trial solution $T^*(x, y)$. The equation turns $-\nabla \varepsilon(x, y) \cdot J^* + \varepsilon(x, y)\nabla \cdot [\kappa^*(x, y) \cdot \nabla T^*(x, y)] = 0$. The first term on the left side is zero, and the equation becomes $\nabla \cdot [\kappa^*(x, y) \cdot \nabla T^*(x, y)] = 0$, which is always valid. Thus, the trial solution is exactly right, i.e., $T'(x, y) = T^*(x, y)$. In other words, new material properties will not affect original streamlines and isotherms. With the definitions of $J'_n = \kappa' |\nabla_n T'|$, $J_n^* = \kappa^* |\nabla_n T^*|$, and $J_n = \kappa |\nabla_n T|$ and the demands for $J'_n = J_n$ and $T' = T^*$, we can further derive $\kappa'(x_0, y_0) = \kappa J_n(y_1(x_0, y_0)) / J_n^*(y_1(x_0, y_0))$, where ∇_n denotes the normal gradient operator. J_n / J_n^* can be acquired by numerical simulation or analytically calculated in regular geometries. With known D' and κ' , we can finally acquire volumetric heat capacity by $\rho' C' = \kappa' / D'$.

We calculate the analytical full parameters in regular geometries below. Though previous pseudo-conformal transformation [5] can produce the full parameters in 2D regular geometries, it does not apply to 3D due to lacking 3D conformal coordinate transformation. On the contrary,

the heat diffusion invariant is still applicable and efficient. We primarily refer to Milton's book [6] to solve the steady-state thermal conduction equation. Our unique contribution is deriving volumetric heat capacity, which might be difficult without the heat diffusion invariant.

Two dimensions

Confocal ellipses. We consider the elliptical coordinate system (μ, ν) ,

$$x = a \cosh \mu \cos \nu, \quad (\text{S15a})$$

$$y = a \sinh \mu \sin \nu, \quad (\text{S15b})$$

where a is the semi-focal length along the x -axis. The inverse transformation is

$$\mu = \operatorname{arcsinh} \sqrt{\frac{a_1 + a_2 - 1 + \sqrt{(a_1 + a_2 - 1)^2 + 4a_2}}{2}}, \quad (\text{S16a})$$

$$\cos \nu = (\operatorname{sign} x) \sqrt{\frac{a_1 + a_2 + 1 - \sqrt{(a_1 + a_2 + 1)^2 - 4a_1}}{2}}, \quad (\text{S16b})$$

with $a_1 = x^2/a^2$ and $a_2 = y^2/a^2$.

We consider a confocal elliptical core-shell structure with inner and outer boundaries of $\mu = \mu_c$ and $\mu = \mu_s$, where μ represents a set of elliptical curve boundaries. If we suppose the temperature gradient along the x -axis, the temperatures in the shell T_s and matrix T_m are

$$T_s = (\lambda_s \cosh \mu + \beta_s \sinh \mu) \cos \nu, \quad (\text{S17a})$$

$$T_m = \lambda_m \cosh \mu \cos \nu, \quad (\text{S17b})$$

where λ_s and β_s are undetermined constants and λ_m is a known constant. The boundary conditions are

$$T_s|_{\mu=\mu_s} = T_m|_{\mu=\mu_s}, \quad (\text{S18a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu} \Big|_{\mu=\mu_c} = 0, \quad (\text{S18b})$$

indicating the TBC and IBC on the outer and inner boundaries. The substitution of Eq. (S17)

into Eq. (S18) yields

$$\lambda_s \cosh \mu_s + \beta_s \sinh \mu_s = \lambda_m \cosh \mu_s, \quad (\text{S19a})$$

$$\lambda_s \sinh \mu_c + \beta_s \cosh \mu_c = 0. \quad (\text{S19b})$$

The solution to Eq. (S19) is

$$\lambda_s = \lambda_m \frac{1}{1 - \tanh \mu_s \tanh \mu_c}, \quad (\text{S20a})$$

$$\beta_s = \lambda_m \frac{1}{\tanh \mu_s - \coth \mu_c}. \quad (\text{S20b})$$

The components of the temperature gradient ∇T_s are

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu} = (\lambda_s \sinh \mu + \beta_s \cosh \mu) \cos \nu, \quad (\text{S21a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \nu} = -(\lambda_s \cosh \mu + \beta_s \sinh \mu) \sin \nu. \quad (\text{S21b})$$

The modulus square of the temperature gradient ∇T_s is

$$|\nabla T_s|^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \nu}\right)^2}{a^2(\sinh^2 \mu + \sin^2 \nu)} = \frac{\lambda_m^2 \{\cosh[2(\mu - \mu_c)] - \cos(2\nu)\} \cosh^2 \mu_s}{a^2 [\cosh(2\mu) - \cos(2\nu)] \cosh^2(\mu_s - \mu_c)}. \quad (\text{S22})$$

We can calculate thermal diffusivity by Eq. (S12),

$$D' = D \frac{|\nabla T_m|^2}{|\nabla T_s|^2} = D \frac{[\cosh(2\mu) - \cos(2\nu)] \cosh^2(\mu_s - \mu_c)}{\{\cosh[2(\mu - \mu_c)] - \cos(2\nu)\} \cosh^2 \mu_s}. \quad (\text{S23})$$

Thermal conductivity is

$$\kappa' = \kappa \frac{|\nabla_n T_m|}{|\nabla_n T_s|} = \kappa \frac{\frac{\partial T_m}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}}{\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}} = \kappa \frac{\lambda_m \sinh \mu_s}{\lambda_s \sinh \mu_s + \beta_s \cosh \mu_s} = \kappa \frac{\tanh \mu_s}{\tanh(\mu_s - \mu_c)}. \quad (\text{S24})$$

Volumetric heat capacity is

$$\rho' C' = \frac{\kappa'}{D'} = \rho C \frac{\{\cosh[2(\mu - \mu_c)] - \cos(2\nu)\} \sinh(2\mu_s)}{[\cosh(2\mu) - \cos(2\nu)] \sinh[2(\mu_s - \mu_c)]}. \quad (\text{S25})$$

Equations (S24) and (S25) are the full parameters of transient thermal cloaking in the x -axis.

On the other hand, if the temperature gradient is along the y -axis, the temperatures in the shell T_s and matrix T_m are

$$T_s = (\lambda_s \sinh \mu + \beta_s \cosh \mu) \sin \nu, \quad (\text{S26a})$$

$$T_m = \lambda_m \sinh \mu \sin \nu. \quad (\text{S26b})$$

With the similar TBC and IBC, we can obtain

$$\lambda_s = \lambda_m \frac{1}{1 - \coth \mu_s \coth \mu_c}, \quad (\text{S27a})$$

$$\beta_s = \lambda_m \frac{1}{\coth \mu_s - \tanh \mu_c}. \quad (\text{S27b})$$

Thermal diffusivity is

$$D' = D \frac{|\nabla T_m|^2}{|\nabla T_s|^2} = D \frac{[\cosh(2\mu) - \cos(2\nu)] \cosh^2(\mu_s - \mu_c)}{\{\cosh[2(\mu - \mu_c)] + \cos(2\nu)\} \sinh^2 \mu_s}. \quad (\text{S28})$$

Thermal conductivity is

$$\kappa' = \kappa \frac{|\nabla_n T_m|}{|\nabla_n T_s|} = \kappa \frac{\frac{\partial T_m}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}}{\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}} = \kappa \frac{\lambda_m \cosh \mu_s}{\lambda_s \sinh \mu_s + \beta_s \cosh \mu_s} = \kappa \frac{\coth \mu_s}{\tanh(\mu_s - \mu_c)}. \quad (\text{S29})$$

Volumetric heat capacity is

$$\rho' C' = \frac{\kappa'}{D'} = \rho C \frac{\{\cosh[2(\mu - \mu_c)] + \cos(2\nu)\} \sinh(2\mu_s)}{[\cosh(2\mu) - \cos(2\nu)] \sinh[2(\mu_s - \mu_c)]}. \quad (\text{S30})$$

Concentric circles. Due to $a \neq 0$ in Eq. (S15), we consider the cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ) for the circular case,

$$x = r \cos \theta, \quad (\text{S31a})$$

$$y = r \sin \theta. \quad (\text{S31b})$$

We consider a circular core-shell structure with inner and outer boundaries of $r = r_c$ and $r = r_s$. Without loss of generality, we assume the temperature gradient along the x -axis. The temperatures in the shell T_s and matrix T_m are

$$T_s = \left(\lambda_s r + \frac{\beta_s}{r} \right) \cos \theta, \quad (\text{S32a})$$

$$T_m = \lambda_m r \cos \theta. \quad (\text{S32b})$$

The boundary conditions are

$$T_s|_{r=r_s} = T_m|_{r=r_s}, \quad (\text{S33a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=r_c} = 0, \quad (\text{S33b})$$

which have the same physical meaning as Eqs. (S18a) and (S18b). Substituting Eq. (S32) into Eq. (S33) yields

$$\lambda_s r_s + \frac{\beta_s}{r_s} = \lambda_m r_s, \quad (\text{S34a})$$

$$\lambda_s - \frac{\beta_s}{r_c^2} = 0. \quad (\text{S34b})$$

The solution to Eq. (S34) is

$$\lambda_s = \lambda_m \frac{1}{1+p}, \quad (\text{S35a})$$

$$\beta_s = \lambda_m \frac{r_c^2}{1+p}, \quad (\text{S35b})$$

where $p = r_c^2/r_s^2$ is the area fraction. The components of the temperature gradient ∇T_s are

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} = \left(\lambda_s - \frac{\beta_s}{r^2} \right) \cos \theta = \frac{\lambda_m}{1+p} \frac{r^2 - r_c^2}{r^2} \cos \theta, \quad (\text{S36a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \theta} = - \left(\lambda_s r + \frac{\beta_s}{r} \right) \sin \theta = - \frac{\lambda_m}{1+p} \frac{r^2 + r_c^2}{r} \sin \theta. \quad (\text{S36b})$$

The modulus square of the temperature gradient ∇T_s is

$$|\nabla T_s|^2 = \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 = \frac{\lambda_m^2}{(1+p)^2} \frac{(r^2 - r_c^2)^2 \cos^2 \theta + (r^2 + r_c^2)^2 \sin^2 \theta}{r^4}. \quad (\text{S37})$$

Thermal diffusivity is

$$D' = D \frac{|\nabla T_m|^2}{|\nabla T_s|^2} = D \frac{(1+p)^2 r^4}{(r^2 + r_c^2)^2 - 4r_c^2 r^2 \cos^2 \theta}. \quad (\text{S38})$$

Thermal conductivity is

$$\kappa' = \kappa \frac{|\nabla_n T_m|}{|\nabla_n T_s|} = \kappa \frac{\frac{\partial T_m}{\partial r}|_{r=r_s}}{\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r}|_{r=r_s}} = \kappa \frac{\lambda_m}{\frac{\lambda_m}{1+p} \frac{r_s^2 - r_c^2}{r_s^2}} = \kappa \frac{1+p}{1-p}. \quad (\text{S39})$$

Volumetric heat capacity is

$$\rho' C' = \frac{\kappa'}{D'} = \rho C \frac{(r^2 + r_c^2)^2 - 4r_c^2 r^2 \cos^2 \theta}{(1-p^2)r^4}. \quad (\text{S40})$$

Three dimensions

Ellipsoids. We consider the ellipsoidal coordinate system (μ, ν, ϕ) ,

$$\frac{x^2}{\mu + a_1^2} + \frac{y^2}{\mu + a_2^2} + \frac{z^2}{\mu + a_3^2} = 1, \quad (\text{S41a})$$

$$\frac{x^2}{\nu + a_1^2} + \frac{y^2}{\nu + a_2^2} + \frac{z^2}{\nu + a_3^2} = 1, \quad (\text{S41b})$$

$$\frac{x^2}{\phi + a_1^2} + \frac{y^2}{\phi + a_2^2} + \frac{z^2}{\phi + a_3^2} = 1, \quad (\text{S41c})$$

where $a_1 > a_2 > a_3$ are the semi-axes of the core. The coordinate μ denotes an ellipsoidal

surface. The inner and outer ellipsoidal surfaces of the shell are denoted by $\mu = \mu_c = 0$ and $\mu = \mu_s$. Equation (S41) produces

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial \mu} = \frac{x}{2(\mu + a_1^2)}, \quad (\text{S42a})$$

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial v} = \frac{x}{2(v + a_1^2)}, \quad (\text{S42b})$$

$$\frac{\partial x}{\partial \phi} = \frac{x}{2(\phi + a_1^2)}. \quad (\text{S42c})$$

With a temperature gradient in the x -axis, the temperatures in the shell T_s and matrix T_m are

$$T_s = [\lambda_s + \beta_s \epsilon(\mu)]x, \quad (\text{S43a})$$

$$T_m = \lambda_m x, \quad (\text{S43b})$$

with the definitions of

$$\epsilon(\mu) = \int_{\mu_c}^{\mu} \frac{d\mu}{(\mu + a_1^2)\psi(\mu)}, \quad (\text{S44a})$$

$$\psi(\mu) = \sqrt{(\mu + a_1^2)(\mu + a_2^2)(\mu + a_3^2)}. \quad (\text{S44b})$$

We can further obtain

$$\epsilon(\mu_c) = 0, \quad (\text{S45a})$$

$$\epsilon(\mu_s) = \frac{2L_c}{\psi(\mu_c)} - \frac{2L_s}{\psi(\mu_s)}, \quad (\text{S45b})$$

$$\frac{\partial[\epsilon(\mu)x]}{\partial \mu} = \frac{x}{2(\mu + a_1^2)} \left[\epsilon(\mu) + \frac{2}{\psi(\mu)} \right], \quad (\text{S45c})$$

where L_c and L_s are the shape factors along the x -axis,

$$L_c = \frac{\psi(\mu_c)}{2} \int_{\mu_c}^{\infty} \frac{d\mu}{(\mu + a_1^2)\psi(\mu)}, \quad (\text{S46a})$$

$$L_s = \frac{\psi(\mu_s)}{2} \int_{\mu_s}^{\infty} \frac{d\mu}{(\mu + a_1^2)\psi(\mu)}. \quad (\text{S46b})$$

The boundary conditions are

$$T_s|_{\mu=\mu_s} = T_m|_{\mu=\mu_s}, \quad (\text{S47a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_c} = 0, \quad (\text{S47b})$$

indicating the TBC and IBC on the outer and inner edges. Substituting Eq. (S43) into Eq. (S47)

further yields

$$\lambda_s + \beta_s \epsilon(\mu_s) = \lambda_m, \quad (\text{S48a})$$

$$\lambda_s + \beta_s \epsilon(\mu_c) + \frac{2\beta_s}{\psi(\mu_c)} = 0. \quad (\text{S48b})$$

The solution to Eq. (S48) is

$$\lambda_s = \lambda_m \frac{1}{1-L_c+pL_s}, \quad (\text{S49a})$$

$$\beta_s = -\lambda_m \frac{\psi(\mu_c)\psi(\mu_s)}{2[\psi(\mu_s)(1-L_c)+\psi(\mu_c)L_s]}, \quad (\text{S49b})$$

where $p = \psi(\mu_c)/\psi(\mu_s)$ is the core's volume fraction. The components of the temperature gradient ∇T_s are

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu} = \frac{x}{2(\mu+a_1^2)} \left[\lambda_s + \beta_s \epsilon(\mu) + \frac{2\beta_s}{\psi(\mu)} \right], \quad (\text{S50a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial v} = \frac{x}{2(v+a_1^2)} [\lambda_s + \beta_s \epsilon(\mu)], \quad (\text{S50b})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \phi} = \frac{x}{2(\phi+a_2^2)} [\lambda_s + \beta_s \epsilon(\mu)]. \quad (\text{S50c})$$

The modulus square of the temperature gradient ∇T_s is

$$|\nabla T_s|^2 = \frac{4 \left[\psi^2(\mu)(v-\phi) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu} \right)^2 + \psi^2(v)(\phi-\mu) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial v} \right)^2 + \psi^2(\phi)(\mu-v) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \phi} \right)^2 \right]}{-(v-\phi)(\phi-\mu)(\mu-v)}. \quad (\text{S51})$$

We can calculate thermal diffusivity by

$$D' = D \frac{|\nabla T_m|^2}{|\nabla T_s|^2} = D \frac{-\lambda_m^2 (v-\phi)(\phi-\mu)(\mu-v)}{4 \left[\psi^2(\mu)(v-\phi) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu} \right)^2 + \psi^2(v)(\phi-\mu) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial v} \right)^2 + \psi^2(\phi)(\mu-v) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \phi} \right)^2 \right]}. \quad (\text{S52})$$

Thermal conductivity is

$$\kappa' = \kappa \frac{|\nabla_n T_m|}{|\nabla_n T_s|} = \kappa \frac{\frac{\partial T_m}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}}{\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}} = \kappa \frac{\lambda_m}{\lambda_s + \beta_s \epsilon(\mu_s) + \frac{2\beta_s}{\psi(\mu_s)}} = \kappa \frac{1-L_c+L_s p}{1-L_c-(1-L_s)p}. \quad (\text{S53})$$

Volumetric heat capacity is

$$\rho' C' = \frac{\kappa'}{D'} = \rho C \frac{1-L_c+L_s p}{1-L_c-(1-L_s)p} \frac{4 \left[\psi^2(\mu)(v-\phi) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu} \right)^2 + \psi^2(v)(\phi-\mu) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial v} \right)^2 + \psi^2(\phi)(\mu-v) \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \phi} \right)^2 \right]}{-\lambda_m^2 (v-\phi)(\phi-\mu)(\mu-v)}, \quad (\text{S54})$$

which is complex but analytical in principle.

Oblate spheroids. The ellipsoidal coordinate system needs $a_1 > a_2 > a_3$, which cannot describe oblate spheroids. We consider the oblate spheroidal coordinate system (μ, ν, ϕ) ,

$$x = a \sinh \mu \sin \nu, \quad (\text{S55a})$$

$$y = a \cosh \mu \cos \nu \cos \phi, \quad (\text{S55b})$$

$$z = a \cosh \mu \cos \nu \sin \phi, \quad (\text{S55c})$$

where a is the semi-focal length along the y -axis. The inverse transformation is

$$\mu = \operatorname{arccosh} \sqrt{\frac{a_1 + a_2 + 1 + \sqrt{(a_1 + a_2 + 1)^2 - 4a_2}}{2}}, \quad (\text{S56a})$$

$$\sin \nu = (\operatorname{sign} x) \sqrt{\frac{-(a_1 + a_2 - 1) + \sqrt{(a_1 + a_2 - 1)^2 + 4a_1}}{2}}, \quad (\text{S56b})$$

with $a_1 = x^2/a^2$ and $a_2 = (y^2 + z^2)/a^2$. We also assume a temperature gradient along the x -axis. The temperatures in the shell T_s and matrix T_m are

$$T_s = [i\lambda_s \sinh \mu + \beta_s(-1 + i\xi \sinh \mu)] \sin \nu, \quad (\text{S57a})$$

$$T_m = \lambda_m \sinh \mu \sin \nu, \quad (\text{S57b})$$

where i is the imaginary unit and $\xi = \log \sqrt{(1 + i \sinh \mu)/(1 - i \sinh \mu)}$ is purely imaginary.

With the similar TBC and IBC, we can obtain

$$\lambda_s = i\lambda_m \frac{[i\xi(\mu_c) \cosh \mu_c - \tanh \mu_c] \sinh \mu_s}{\{i[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \sinh \mu_s - 1\} \cosh \mu_c + \sinh \mu_s \tanh \mu_c}, \quad (\text{S58a})$$

$$\beta_s = \lambda_m \frac{\sinh \mu_s \cosh \mu_c}{\{i[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \sinh \mu_s - 1\} \cosh \mu_c + \sinh \mu_s \tanh \mu_c}, \quad (\text{S58b})$$

where λ_s is purely imaginary and β_s is a real number. The components of the temperature gradient ∇T_s are

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu} = [i\lambda_s \cosh \mu + \beta_s(-\tanh \mu + i\xi \cosh \mu)] \sin \nu, \quad (\text{S59a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \nu} = [i\lambda_s \sinh \mu + \beta_s(-1 + i\xi \sinh \mu)] \cos \nu. \quad (\text{S59b})$$

The modulus square of the temperature gradient ∇T_s is

$$|\nabla T_s|^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \nu}\right)^2}{a^2(\sinh^2 \mu + \sin^2 \nu)}. \quad (\text{S60})$$

We can calculate thermal diffusivity by

$$D' = D \frac{|\nabla T_m|^2}{|\nabla T_s|^2} = \frac{\lambda_m^2(\sinh^2 \mu + \sin^2 \nu)}{\left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \nu}\right)^2}. \quad (\text{S61})$$

Thermal conductivity is

$$\kappa' = \kappa \frac{\frac{\partial T_m}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}}{\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}} = \kappa \frac{\{i[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \sinh \mu_s - 1\} \cosh \mu_c + \sinh \mu_s \tanh \mu_c}{i[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \sinh \mu_s \cosh \mu_c + \sinh \mu_s \tanh \mu_c - \tanh^2 \mu_s \cosh \mu_c}. \quad (\text{S62})$$

Volumetric heat capacity is

$$\rho' C' = \rho C \frac{\{i[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \sinh \mu_s - 1\} \cosh \mu_c + \sinh \mu_s \tanh \mu_c}{i[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \sinh \mu_s \cosh \mu_c + \sinh \mu_s \tanh \mu_c - \tanh^2 \mu_s \cosh \mu_c} \frac{\left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial v}\right)^2}{\lambda_m^2 (\sinh^2 \mu + \sin^2 v)}. \quad (\text{S63})$$

Prolate spheroids. We consider the prolate spheroidal coordinate system (μ, ν, ϕ) ,

$$x = a \cosh \mu \cos \nu, \quad (\text{S64a})$$

$$y = a \sinh \mu \sin \nu \cos \phi, \quad (\text{S64b})$$

$$z = a \sinh \mu \sin \nu \sin \phi, \quad (\text{S64c})$$

where a is the semi-focal length along the x -axis. The inverse transformation is

$$\mu = \operatorname{arcsinh} \sqrt{\frac{a_1 + a_2 - 1 + \sqrt{(a_1 + a_2 - 1)^2 + 4a_2}}{2}}, \quad (\text{S65a})$$

$$\cos \nu = (\operatorname{sign} x) \sqrt{\frac{a_1 + a_2 + 1 - \sqrt{(a_1 + a_2 + 1)^2 - 4a_1}}{2}}, \quad (\text{S65b})$$

with $a_1 = x^2/a^2$ and $a_2 = (y^2 + z^2)/a^2$. We also assume a temperature gradient along the x -axis. The temperatures in the shell T_s and matrix T_m are

$$T_s = [\lambda_s \cosh \mu + \beta_s (-1 + \xi \cosh \mu)] \cos \nu, \quad (\text{S66a})$$

$$T_m = \lambda_m \cosh \mu \cos \nu, \quad (\text{S66b})$$

where $\xi = \log \sqrt{(1 + \cosh \mu)/(1 - \cosh \mu)}$ is a complex number due to $\cosh \mu > 1$. With the similar TBC and FBC, we can obtain

$$\lambda_s = \lambda_m \frac{[-\xi(\mu_c) \sinh \mu_c + \coth \mu_c] \cosh \mu_s}{\{[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \cosh \mu_s - 1\} \sinh \mu_c + \cosh \mu_s \coth \mu_c}, \quad (\text{S67a})$$

$$\beta_s = \lambda_m \frac{\cosh \mu_s \sinh \mu_c}{\{[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \cosh \mu_s - 1\} \sinh \mu_c + \cosh \mu_s \coth \mu_c}, \quad (\text{S67b})$$

where λ_s is complex and β_s is real. The components of the temperature gradient ∇T_s are

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu} = [\lambda_s \sinh \mu + \beta_s (-\coth \mu + \xi \sinh \mu)] \cos \nu, \quad (\text{S68a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial v} = -[\lambda_s \cosh \mu + \beta_s (-1 + \xi \cosh \mu)] \sin \nu. \quad (\text{S68b})$$

The modulus square of the temperature gradient ∇T_s is

$$|\nabla T_s|^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \nu}\right)^2}{a^2(\sinh^2 \mu + \sin^2 \nu)}. \quad (\text{S69})$$

We can calculate thermal diffusivity by

$$D' = D \frac{|\nabla T_m|^2}{|\nabla T_s|^2} = \frac{\lambda_m^2(\sinh^2 \mu + \sin^2 \nu)}{\left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \nu}\right)^2}. \quad (\text{S70})$$

Thermal conductivity is

$$\kappa' = \kappa \frac{\frac{\partial T_m}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}}{\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}|_{\mu=\mu_s}} = \kappa \frac{\{[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \cosh \mu_s - 1\} \sinh \mu_c + \cosh \mu_s \coth \mu_c}{[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \cosh \mu_s \sinh \mu_c + \cosh \mu_s \coth \mu_c - \coth^2 \mu_s \sinh \mu_c}. \quad (\text{S71})$$

Volumetric heat capacity is

$$\rho' C' = \rho C \frac{\{[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \cosh \mu_s - 1\} \sinh \mu_c + \cosh \mu_s \coth \mu_c}{[\xi(\mu_s) - \xi(\mu_c)] \cosh \mu_s \sinh \mu_c + \cosh \mu_s \coth \mu_c - \coth^2 \mu_s \sinh \mu_c} \frac{\left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \mu}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \nu}\right)^2}{\lambda_m^2(\sinh^2 \mu + \sin^2 \nu)}. \quad (\text{S72})$$

Spheroids. We consider the spherical coordinate system (r, θ, ϕ) ,

$$x = r \cos \theta, \quad (\text{S73a})$$

$$y = r \sin \theta \cos \phi, \quad (\text{S73b})$$

$$z = r \sin \theta \sin \phi. \quad (\text{S73c})$$

The temperatures in the shell T_s and matrix T_m are

$$T_s = \left(\lambda_s r + \frac{\beta_s}{r^2} \right) \cos \theta, \quad (\text{S74a})$$

$$T_m = \lambda_m r \cos \theta. \quad (\text{S74b})$$

The boundary conditions are

$$T_s|_{r=r_s} = T_m|_{r=r_s}, \quad (\text{S75a})$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r}|_{r=r_c} = 0. \quad (\text{S75b})$$

Substituting Eq. (S74) into Eq. (S75) yields

$$\lambda_s r_s + \frac{\beta_s}{r_s^2} = \lambda_m r_s, \quad (\text{S76a})$$

$$\lambda_s - \frac{2\beta_s}{r_c^3} = 0. \quad (\text{S76b})$$

The solution to Eq. (S76) is

$$\lambda_s = \lambda_m \frac{2}{2+p}, \quad (S77a)$$

$$\beta_s = \lambda_m \frac{r_c^3}{2+p}, \quad (S77b)$$

where $p = r_c^3/r_s^3$ is the core's volume fraction. The temperature gradient components are

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} = \left(\lambda_s - \frac{2\beta_s}{r^3} \right) \cos \theta = \frac{2\lambda_m}{2+p} \frac{r^3 - r_c^3}{r^3} \cos \theta, \quad (S78a)$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \theta} = - \left(\lambda_s r + \frac{\beta_s}{r^2} \right) \sin \theta = - \frac{\lambda_m}{2+p} \frac{2r^3 + r_c^3}{r^2} \sin \theta, \quad (S78b)$$

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \phi} = 0. \quad (S78c)$$

The modulus square of the temperature gradient $|\nabla T_s|$ is

$$|\nabla T_s|^2 = \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \phi} \right)^2 = \frac{\lambda_m^2}{(2+p)^2} \frac{4(r^3 - r_c^3)^2 \cos^2 \theta + (2r^3 + r_c^3)^2 \sin^2 \theta}{r^6}. \quad (S79)$$

Thermal diffusivity is

$$D' = D \frac{|\nabla T_m|^2}{|\nabla T_s|^2} = D \frac{(2+p)^2 r^6}{(2r^3 + r_c^3)^2 - 3r_c^3(4r^3 - r_c^3) \cos^2 \theta}. \quad (S80)$$

Thermal conductivity is

$$\kappa' = \kappa \frac{|\nabla_n T_m|}{|\nabla_n T_s|} = \kappa \frac{\frac{\partial T_m}{\partial r}|_{r=r_s}}{\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r}|_{r=r_s}} = \kappa \frac{\lambda_m}{\frac{2\lambda_m}{2+p} \frac{r_s^3 - r_c^3}{r_s^3}} = \kappa \frac{2+p}{2(1-p)}. \quad (S81)$$

Volumetric heat capacity is

$$\rho' C' = \frac{\kappa'}{D'} = \rho C \frac{(2r^3 + r_c^3)^2 - 3r_c^3(4r^3 - r_c^3) \cos^2 \theta}{2(1-p)(2+p)r^6}. \quad (S82)$$

Without loss of generality, we perform simulations to verify Eqs. (S81) and (S82). Thermal diffusivity has infinite values on the inner boundary [Fig. S1(a)]. The thermal conductivity from Eq. (S81) is uniform [Fig. S1(b)]. The volumetric heat capacity from Eq. (S82) is displayed in Fig. S1(c). The temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s are shown in Figs. S1(d)-S1(f), whose $z-x$ cross-sections are presented in Figs. S1(g)-S1(i). We also plot the temperature deviation $\xi = \frac{T - T_{\text{ref}}}{T_1 - T_r} \times 100\%$ at three points. The evolutions of ξ with and without cloaking are demonstrated in Figs. S1(j)-S1(l). The zero temperature deviation ($\xi = 0$) over time verifies accurate transient thermal cloaking in 3D.

Note 4. Effective thermal diffusivity

Effective thermal diffusivity can be given by $D_e = \kappa_e / \rho_e C_e$, where the subscripts denote the effective values. The Maxwell-Garnett formula [6] predicts $\kappa_e = \kappa_2 \frac{\kappa_1 + \kappa_2 + (\kappa_1 - \kappa_2)p}{\kappa_1 + \kappa_2 - (\kappa_1 - \kappa_2)p}$, where κ_1 and κ_2 are the thermal conductivity of the particle and matrix, and p is the area fraction of the particle. The weighted average method predicts $\rho_e C_e = p\rho_1 C_1 + (1 - p)\rho_2 C_2$, where $\rho_1 C_1$ and $\rho_2 C_2$ denote the volumetric heat capacity of the particle and matrix. The approach also applies to other continuous volumetric heat capacity $\rho_3 C_3$, i.e., $\rho_e C_e = \frac{\int_{\Omega} \rho_3 C_3 d\Omega}{\int_{\Omega} d\Omega}$, where Ω denotes the structural region. We take the above spherical thermal cloak as an example. When $\rho_3 C_3$ takes Eq. (S82) in the shell and 0 in the core, we can then obtain $\rho_e C_e = \rho C$. Thus, the weighted average method is compatible with the heat diffusion invariant.

We should determine the practical thermal diffusivity of a structure and compare it with the value predicted by the effective medium theory. Unlike effective thermal conductivity, which can be numerically obtained from an average heat flux divided by a negative average temperature gradient, effective thermal diffusivity has no analogical formula. Since thermal diffusivity depicts the ability of temperature to reach identity, it crucially affects transient heat transfer, making the temperature evolution of specific thermal diffusivity unique. First, we establish a correlation between thermal diffusivity and temperature as a reference. Then, we compare the temperature of a practical structure with that reference and determine the practical thermal diffusivity. The detailed process is introduced below.

We construct a uniform structure with a size of $1 \times 0.1 \text{ m}^2$ [Fig. S2(a)]. The left edge is a constant high temperature of $T = 1 \text{ K}$. The right is thermal insulation. The upper and lower are periodic conditions with continuous temperature and heat flux. The initial temperature is

$T = 0$ K. We focus on the average temperature on the middle line. We set different thermal diffusivity and demonstrate the average temperature at three certain times [Fig. S2(a)]. The correlation between thermal diffusivity and temperature is established as a reference.

Then, we consider a practical structure with periodic brown particles embedded in the blue matrix [Fig. S2(b)]. The boundary and initial conditions are the same as in Fig. S2(a). We set the area fraction of the brown particles p as a variable. Varying p causes different effective thermal diffusivity and average temperature [Fig. S2(b)]. We compare this temperature with the reference in Fig. S2(a) and obtain the effective thermal diffusivity [the top inset in Fig. 3(a)].

We utilize the effective medium theory to design the sample [Fig. 3(b)]. The background is 316L stainless steel. The shell is divided into three parts. The top and bottom parts are 316L stainless steel, while the middle part is lead. The core (cloaked) region is air for implementing thermal insulation. The sample is divided into 20×20 squares. The radius of the air holes in the background is 3.56 mm. We drill air holes in the middle part due to the low volumetric heat capacity. Differently, we fill the holes in the top and bottom parts with thermal grease due to the high volumetric heat capacity. The sample is tightly pressed utilizing the high-pressure mechanical embedding technology to reduce interfacial thermal resistance. The upper surface is covered with a polypropylene film to relieve the interference from infrared reflection. The bottom surface, front, and rear sides are covered with insulation foam tapes to avoid the influence of natural thermal convection. We immerse the supports at the two ends of the sample in tanks with hot and cold water.

We further perform simulations based on three practical structures: Bare, Cloak, and Reference. In the Bare case [Figs. S3(a)-S3(d)], the isotherms in the background are disturbed

apparently. The Cloak [Figs. S3(e)-S3(h)] and Reference [Figs. S3(i)-S3(l)] cases demonstrate similar undisturbed temperature profiles. The values of η are 0.139%, 0.255%, 0.255%, and 0.240% for the Bare case [Figs. S3(a)-S3(d)], and those values are 0.030%, 0.030%, 0.030%, and 0.027% for the Cloak case [Figs. S3(e)-S3(h)]. Thus, our structure does work because it makes η smaller in one order of magnitude.

Note 5. Omnidirectional functionalities

We show two omnidirectional functionalities (a cloak and a concentrator-rotator) to prove that the heat diffusion invariant is not limited to unidirectional functionalities.

Omnidirectional cloaking

First, we extend the unidirectional transient cloaking in the main text to omnidirectional. We directly consider a more complex geometry than the geometry in the main text. The main purpose is to make the geometry more anisotropic, thereby magnifying the directionality issue and proving the robustness of the heat diffusion invariant. To this end, roughly three steps are involved in determining the ideal parameters.

Step 1 (same as what has been done in the main text): Take a freeform geometry. Consider steady-state heat conduction and use the TBC. Obtain the temperature profile (T_1) and the mesh comprising streamlines and isotherms. Design isotropic thermal conductivity (κ_1) to match the boundary normal heat flux. Design volumetric heat capacity ($\rho_1 C_1$) based on the heat diffusion invariant. The parameter profiles and simulation results are shown in Figs. S4(a)-S4(d).

Step 2 (similar to Step 1, but consider the orthogonal direction): Take the same freeform geometry. Consider steady-state heat conduction and apply the heat flux boundary condition in

the vertical direction. Get the temperature profile (T_2) and the mesh comprising streamlines and isotherms. Due to the duality of streamlines and isotherms in a harmonic function, this mesh is the same as in Step 1 as long as exchanging the streamlines and isotherms. Design isotropic thermal conductivity (κ_2) to match the boundary tangential temperature gradient. Design volumetric heat capacity ($\rho_2 C_2$) based on the heat diffusion invariant. The parameter profiles and simulation results are shown in Figs. S4(e)-S4(h).

Step 3 (key to omnidirectionality): Steps 1 and 2 employ isotropic thermal conductivity to implement unidirectional cloaking. Since streamlines and isotherms are orthogonal in isotropic media, they can form a local coordinate system. In Step 1, thermal conductivity (κ_1) is isotropic, its expression in the local coordinate system is a diagonalized tensor with two same eigenvalues (κ_1). However, only the eigenvalue whose eigenvector follows streamlines works, and the other one does not, which can take any value and act as an extra degree of freedom. In fact, as long as that useless component takes the thermal conductivity derived in Step 2 (κ_2), omnidirectional thermal cloaking can be achieved. The anisotropic thermal conductivity can be expressed in the local coordinate system as a diagonalized tensor with two different eigenvalues of κ_1 and κ_2 , i.e., $\begin{bmatrix} \kappa_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \kappa_2 \end{bmatrix}$, which can be re-expressed in the Cartesian coordinate system as

$$\vec{\kappa} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} \kappa_1(\partial_x T_1)^2 + \kappa_2(\partial_y T_1)^2 & (\kappa_1 - \kappa_2)\partial_x T_1 \partial_y T_1 \\ (\kappa_1 - \kappa_2)\partial_x T_1 \partial_y T_1 & \kappa_1(\partial_y T_1)^2 + \kappa_2(\partial_x T_1)^2 \end{bmatrix}}{(\partial_x T_1)^2 + (\partial_y T_1)^2}, \quad (\text{S83})$$

which is distinctly different from that predicted by transformation thermotics. Note that $\vec{\kappa}$ and $\begin{bmatrix} \kappa_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \kappa_2 \end{bmatrix}$ are just the expressions in different coordinate systems and essentially refer to the same thermal conductivity. We can further calculate volumetric heat capacity based on the heat diffusion invariant,

$$\rho C = \kappa_1(\partial_x T_1)^2 + \kappa_1(\partial_y T_1)^2. \quad (\text{S84})$$

This example explains why we persist in defining the heat diffusion invariant in an anisotropic form. Based on $\vec{\kappa}$ and ρC , we can realize omnidirectional transient thermal cloaking, whose simulation results (at 0, 30, 60, and 90 degrees) are presented in Figs. S4(i)-S4(p). Please pay special attention to 30 and 60 degrees, which demonstrate accurate cloaking, though we design $\vec{\kappa}$ by considering only 0 and 90 degrees at the beginning. The physical reason is the equivalence between omnidirectional invisibility and invisibility in orthogonal directions. Just because $\vec{\kappa}$ is constructed by considering those 0 and 90 degrees, the temperature profiles in Figs. S4(m) and S4(n) [or Figs. S4(o) and S4(p)] are the same as those in Figs. S4(c) and S4(d) [or Figs. S4(g) and S4(h)].

We then use four steps to construct a practical structure to achieve $\vec{\kappa}$ and ρC .

Step 1: Discretize thermal conductivity. Since the anisotropic thermal conductivity given by Eq. (S83) is diagonalized in the local coordinate system established by the streamlines and isotherms. We discretize the structure based on the streamlines and employ layered structures to realize the anisotropic thermal conductivity [Fig. S5(a)].

Step 2: Re-calculate volumetric heat capacity. The heat diffusion invariant is always valid, and thus, we can re-calculate volumetric heat capacity with the discretized thermal conductivity [Fig. S5(b)], which has the same surface average as in Fig. S4.

Step 3: Coarse-grained volumetric heat capacity. We simplify the volumetric heat capacity according to two factors: 1. Keep constant volumetric heat capacity where thermal conductivity is constant for convenience of finding the corresponding practical material; 2. Use the surface average method to predict the constant volumetric heat capacity of a chosen region. The final volumetric heat capacity is shown in Fig. S5(c).

Step 4: Find practical materials. The principle is using materials that meet the theoretical demand as much as possible and keep the final surface average of the volumetric heat capacity unchanged. The practical materials (readily available on the market) are shown in Fig. S5(d), whose detailed parameters are listed in Table S1.

The simulation results (at 0, 30, 60, and 90 degrees) according to the parameters in Figs. S5(a) and S5(c) are exhibited in Figs. S5(e)-S5(l). Those based on the practical materials in Fig. S5(d) are demonstrated in Figs. S5(m)-S5(t). Thus, omnidirectional transient cloaking is confirmed numerically.

Omnidirectional concentrating-rotating

Besides cloaking, concentrating and rotating are two other typical functionalities. To add difficulty, we aim to concentrate and rotate heat flux simultaneously. This requirement can be realized by constant anisotropic thermal conductivity [7], which transformation thermotics is hard to predict. However, its generalization to transients remains challenging. The anisotropic thermal conductivity (expressed in the cylindrical coordinate system) is

$$\vec{\kappa}' = \begin{bmatrix} \kappa'_{rr} & \kappa'_{r\theta} \\ \kappa'_{\theta r} & \kappa'_{\theta\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \kappa \begin{bmatrix} m & -\alpha m \\ -\alpha m & \alpha^2 m + 1/m \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{S85})$$

The value of m determines the concentration ratio ϑ (i.e., the central heat flux ratio to the background heat flux),

$$\vartheta = \left(\frac{r_c}{r_s}\right)^{-1+1/m}, \quad (\text{S86})$$

where r_c and r_s are the inner and outer radii of the rotator. $m > 1$ is a concentrator-rotator; $m = 1$ is a normal rotator; $m \ll 1$ is a cloak-rotator. α is related to the anticlockwise rotation angle θ_0 ,

$$\alpha = \frac{\theta_0}{\ln r_s - \ln r_c}. \quad (\text{S87})$$

The temperatures in the core T_c and shell T_s are

$$T_c = \lambda_m \vartheta r \cos(\theta - \theta_0), \quad (\text{S88a})$$

$$T_s = \lambda_m \left(\frac{r}{r_s}\right)^{-1+1/m} r \cos(\theta + \alpha \ln r + \alpha \ln r_s). \quad (\text{S88b})$$

With the diffusion invariant described by Eq. (S12), we can derive the volumetric heat capacity of the core $\rho'_c C'_c$,

$$\rho'_c C'_c = \rho_c C_c \vartheta^2. \quad (\text{S89})$$

That of the shell $\rho'_s C'_s$ is

$$\rho'_s C'_s = \frac{\rho_s C_s}{\kappa \lambda_m^2} \partial_i T_s \kappa_{ij} \partial_j T_s = \frac{\rho_s C_s}{\kappa \lambda_m^2} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} & \frac{\partial T_s}{r \partial \theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \kappa'_{rr} & \kappa'_{r\theta} \\ \kappa'_{\theta r} & \kappa'_{\theta\theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial r} \\ \frac{\partial T_s}{r \partial \theta} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{S90})$$

The substitution of Eqs. (S85) and (S88b) into Eq. (S90) yields

$$\rho'_s C'_s = \frac{\rho_s C_s}{m} \left(\frac{r}{r_s}\right)^{2(-1+1/m)}. \quad (\text{S91})$$

We display the radial component of Eq. (S85) in Fig. S6(a), i.e., κ'_{rr} . The volumetric heat capacity from Eqs. (S89) and (S91) are presented in Fig. S6(b). We also employ the practical layered structure to equivalent the ideal anisotropic thermal conductivity [Fig. S6(c)]. To this end, the parametric curve is described by

$$x = r \cos\left(\varrho \ln \frac{r}{r_c} + \theta_0\right), \quad (\text{S92a})$$

$$y = -r \sin\left(\varrho \ln \frac{r}{r_c} + \theta_0\right), \quad (\text{S92b})$$

with the definition of

$$\varrho = \frac{2\alpha m^2}{m^2 - 1 - \alpha^2 m^2 + \sqrt{(m^2 + 1 + \alpha^2 m^2)^2 - 4m^2}}. \quad (\text{S93})$$

The isotropic thermal conductivity of the two materials are

$$\kappa_1 = \kappa_{\parallel} + \sqrt{\kappa_{\parallel}(\kappa_{\parallel} - \kappa_{\perp})}, \quad (\text{S94a})$$

$$\kappa_2 = \kappa_{\parallel} - \sqrt{\kappa_{\parallel}(\kappa_{\parallel} - \kappa_{\perp})}, \quad (\text{S94b})$$

where κ_{\parallel} and κ_{\perp} are the eigenvalues of Eq. (S85),

$$\kappa_{\parallel} = \frac{m^2 + 1 + \alpha^2 m^2 + \sqrt{(m^2 + 1 + \alpha^2 m^2)^2 - 4m^2}}{2m}, \quad (\text{S95a})$$

$$\kappa_{\perp} = \frac{m^2 + 1 + \alpha^2 m^2 - \sqrt{(m^2 + 1 + \alpha^2 m^2)^2 - 4m^2}}{2m}. \quad (\text{S95b})$$

The volumetric heat capacity is shown in Fig. S6(d). The temperature evolutions of these two designs are exhibited in Figs. S6(e)-S6(h). The temperature profile in the background is not distorted. The heat flux in the central area changes direction and becomes larger (denoted by blue arrows). These features confirm a transient thermal concentrator-rotator. We also apply a vertical temperature gradient, and the expected effect remains unchanged [Figs. S6(i)-S6(l)], confirming an omnidirectional metamaterial.

Note 6. Complex-shape functionalities

We take a 2D topologically nontrivial geometry [Fig. S7(a)]. The square length is 0.5 m. The major and minor semi-axes of the middle ellipse are 0.2 and 0.1 m. Those of the top and bottom ellipses are 0.1 and 0.05 m, with a distance of 0.36 m. We set the TBC and IBC to the outer and inner boundaries. We generate thermal diffusivity by Eq. (S12) [Fig. S7(b)]. Thermal conductivity [Fig. S7(c)] and volumetric heat capacity [Fig. S7(d)] are calculated through $\kappa' = \kappa J_n / J_n^*$ and $\rho' C' = \kappa' / D'$. The simulation size is $1 \times 1 \text{ m}^2$. The left and right boundaries are set at $T_l = 1$ and $T_r = 0$ K. The initial temperature is 0 K. The temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s are demonstrated in Figs. S7(e)-S7(g). The value of η with designed κ' and $\rho' C'$ is zero over time [Fig. S7(h)], confirming accurate transient thermal cloaking. If we only design κ' , the transient process is no longer invisible due to $\eta \neq 0$. Invisibility is achieved when reaching the steady state because κ' determines the steady state. The value of η is nonzero without parameter design (i.e., the bare case with only the IBC).

Transient 3D problems are far more complex than 2D. Though inverse design works in principle, computing requirements increase dramatically. The heat diffusion invariant remains accurate and efficient. We consider another complex 3D geometry [Fig. S7(i)]. The outer boundary is a cone whose middle, side radii, and length are 0.36, 0.12, and 0.72 m. The inner boundary is an octahedron of two pyramids whose base length and height are $0.27\sqrt{2}$ and 0.27 m. We apply the TBC and IBC to the outer and inner boundaries. A bulk point with coordinates of (x_0, y_0, z_0) is mapped by a streamline to a boundary point with coordinates of (y_1, z_1) . We export the streamlines from COMSOL Multiphysics and import them back as two three-element interpolation functions to map (x_0, y_0, z_0) to (y_1, z_1) . The full parameters are shown in Figs. S7(j)-S7(l). The simulation size is $1 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ m}^3$. The temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s are shown in Figs. S7(m)-S7(o). The quantitative comparison [Fig. S7(p)] confirms that the heat diffusion invariant precisely controls transient 3D thermal conduction.

Note 7. Flux boundary condition

The thermal conductivity of steady-state cloaking for a definite geometry is not unique. We use the TBC and IBC in the main text. For completeness, we construct a thermal cloak using the flux boundary condition (FBC) below.

We set the boundary normal heat flux as $\hat{n} \cdot J$, where J is the heat flux in the background, and \hat{n} is the boundary normal unit vector [Fig. S8(a)]. We consider a uniform temperature gradient along the x -direction, resulting in $\hat{n} \cdot J = n_x J_x$, where J_x is a constant, and the subscripts are the x -components. The boundary normal heat flux is matched, but the boundary temperature is not, leading to the unmatched boundary tangential temperature gradient. The

temperature gradient is inversely proportional to thermal conductivity for fixed heat flux. To match the tangential temperature gradient, we tailor thermal conductivity κ' along isotherms,

$$\kappa'(x_0, y_0) = \kappa \frac{|\nabla_{\mathbf{t}} T^*(x_1(x_0, y_0))|}{|\nabla_{\mathbf{t}} T(x_1(x_0, y_0))|}, \quad (\text{S96})$$

where $\nabla_{\mathbf{t}}$ is the tangential gradient operator. An isotherm maps a bulk point with coordinates of (x_0, y_0) to a boundary point with a horizontal coordinate of x_1 . Thermal conductivity with Eq. (S96) is shown in Fig. S8(b).

We cannot directly obtain thermal diffusivity due to $T' \neq T^*$. The relation between T' and T^* is

$$|\nabla T'(x_0, y_0)| = |\nabla T^*(x_0, y_0)| \frac{|\nabla_{\mathbf{t}} T(x_1(x_0, y_0))|}{|\nabla_{\mathbf{t}} T^*(x_1(x_0, y_0))|}. \quad (\text{S97})$$

We can calculate thermal diffusivity by Eq. (S12). Volumetric heat capacity is

$$\rho' C'(x_0, y_0) = \frac{\kappa'(x_0, y_0)}{D'(x_0, y_0)} = \rho C \frac{|\nabla T^*(x_0, y_0)|^2}{G^2} \frac{|\nabla_{\mathbf{t}} T(x_1(x_0, y_0))|}{|\nabla_{\mathbf{t}} T^*(x_1(x_0, y_0))|}, \quad (\text{S98})$$

which is demonstrated in Fig. S8(c).

Equations (S96) and (S98) constitute another set of full parameters. The maximum thermal conductivity is $\kappa'/\kappa = 1.7$ [Fig. S8(b)], which is lower than $\kappa'/\kappa = 2.5$ in Fig. 2(c) and may bring convenience to fabrication. The temperature profiles [Figs. S8(d)-S8(f)] and temperature deviation evolutions [Figs. S8(g)-S8(i)] confirm accurate transient thermal cloaking.

For practical implementation, we replace the IBC with extremely low thermal conductivity [Fig. S9(a)]. Since this operation does not influence the outside mesh, the full parameters outside the thin shell remain unchanged and are not shown repeatedly. Yet, the isotherms enter the thin shell, so the parameters of the thin shell need an extra design. The full parameters are shown in Figs. S9(b) and S9(c), enabling precise transient thermal cloaking [Figs. S9(d)-S9(f)]. Insulation materials meet the general requirement for thermal cloaking because we do not need

to design the parameters of the central “object.” We also do not need to tailor the parameters of the insulation shell because the two lines almost coincide in Figs. S9(g)-S9(i). Thus, insulation materials apply to both steady and transient states to satisfy the thermal cloaking requirement, which can replace the IBC effectively.

Note 8. Constant temperature boundary condition

Besides the IBC for constructing insulation thermal cloaking, the constant temperature boundary condition [8] (CTBC, a special case of TBC) enables zero-index thermal cloaking. The inner boundary is set at the average temperature of the hot and cold sources, i.e., 0.5 K [Fig. S10(a)]. The full parameters are demonstrated in Figs. S10(b) and S10(c). The thermal conductivity of the shell is smaller than that of the background [Fig. S10(b)], significantly reducing the extremely high thermal conductivity requirement. Volumetric heat capacity still possesses zero values, whose positions move to the top and bottom corners of the inner edge [Fig. S10(c)].

We also perform simulations for validation [Figs. S10(d)-S10(f)]. The isotherms in the matrix are not distorted. The quantitative evolutions of temperature deviation confirm precise transient zero-index thermal cloaking [Figs. S10(g) and S10(h)]. Since the CTBC does not apply directly to transient heat transfer, we should know the temperature evolution at the central point in advance. For this purpose, we consider a uniform reference structure and export the temperature evolution at the central point [Fig. S10(i)]. The temperature evolution on the inner boundary, marked by the rhombus in Figs. S10(d)-S10(f), is set according to Fig. S10(i), which is independent of position but dependent on time, requiring artificial temperature control.

The precognition of the central temperature evolution is not always available, and artificial temperature control is particularly challenging. We further utilize a highly conductive material [9] as an inner shell to replace the CTBC [Fig. S11(a)]. The mesh outside the thin shell is the same as in Fig. S10(a), indicating the identical parameters outside, which are not demonstrated repeatedly. Since the streamlines enter the thin shell, we should design the parameters of this shell and its inner. The parameters are shown in Figs. S11(b)-S11(f). The thermal conductivity of the core does not require an extra design because the streamlines do not enter there. The simulation results are presented in Figs. S11(g)-S11(i). The temperature derivation evolutions quantitatively verify transient thermal cloaking [Figs. S11(j)-S11(l)]. We design the volumetric heat capacity of the “object” [Fig. S11(f)] to realize precise transient thermal cloaking. This operation does not meet the general requirement for thermal cloaking: any object can be placed inside the cloak without affecting the matrix temperature. Thus, highly conductive materials only yield quasi-cloaking in transient heat conduction because the parameters of the central object are not at will.

We add an insulation shell inside the highly conductive shell to turn quasi-cloaking into cloaking [Fig. S12(a)]. The insulation shell isolates the central area and almost does not change the outside mesh, implying that the parameters are identical to Figs. S11(d) and S11(e). Since the streamlines do not go into the insulation shell and central object, their thermal conductivity does not need an extra design, and their volumetric heat capacity is demonstrated in Figs. S12(b) and S12(c). The temperature distributions [Figs. S12(d)-S12(f)] and the temperature deviation evolutions [Figs. S12(g)-S12(i)] verify precise transient thermal cloaking. Suppose we do not employ the parameters in Figs. S12(b) and S12(c), the temperature deviation evolutions remain

near zero [Figs. S12(g)-S12(i)]. There is no need to design the parameters of the “object,” which indicates true thermal cloaking. Therefore, thermally superconductive materials can effectively replace the CTBC at only the steady state. For a transient state, insulation materials remain necessary to construct transient thermal cloaking in a strict sense.

Note 9. Convective or radiative transparency

The heat diffusion invariant is universal for other heat transfer modes and functionalities. Thermal transparency [10] is a typical functionality that does not require thermal insulation. We discuss its realization in thermal convection and radiation below.

Porous media are a primary model for heat conduction and convection, governed by

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-\kappa \nabla T + \rho_f C_f v T) = 0, \quad (\text{S99})$$

where $\rho_f C_f$ is the volumetric heat capacity of the fluids. The Darcy law depicts the convective velocity of the fluids,

$$v = -\mu \nabla P, \quad (\text{S100})$$

where $\mu = \gamma/\zeta$ is the convective coefficient with the permeability of porous media γ and dynamic viscosity of fluids ζ , and P is pressure. Since the Darcy and Fourier laws have the same equation forms, the designs of μ and κ should be identical. We consider the same geometry as Fig. S7(a). However, no IBC is used [Fig. S13(a)]. The initial thermal conductivity is inhomogeneous, with the upper and lower two ellipses of 2κ and the middle of 0.5κ . Thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity, the effective values of porous media (solids plus fluids), are shown in Figs. S13(b) and S13(c). The convective coefficient is the same as thermal conductivity [Fig. S13(d)]. The temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s are

presented in Figs. S13(e)-S13(g). The pressure profile is shown in Fig. S13(h). The straight isolines in the background in Figs. S13(e)-S13(h) confirm accurate transient conductive and convective transparency.

The Rosseland diffusion approximation characterizes thermal radiation in optically thick media. The radiative heat flux J_R is described by

$$J_R = -\beta T^3 \nabla T, \quad (\text{S101})$$

where $\beta = 16n^2\sigma/(3\zeta)$ is the radiative coefficient with the relative refractive index n , the Stefan-Boltzmann constant σ , and the Rosseland mean extinction coefficient ζ . The governing equation for transient thermal conduction and radiation is

$$\rho C \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-\kappa \nabla T - \beta T^3 \nabla T) = 0. \quad (\text{S102})$$

The total conductive and radiative heat flux is

$$J = -\kappa \left(1 + \frac{\beta T^3}{\kappa} \right) \nabla T. \quad (\text{S103})$$

We perform a variable substitution,

$$\Phi = T + \frac{\beta T^4}{4\kappa}. \quad (\text{S104})$$

Equation (S103) can be rewritten as

$$J = -\kappa \nabla \Phi, \quad (\text{S105})$$

indicating a linear constitutive relation. Since this operation needs a constant β/κ , the designs of β and κ should be identical. We consider a similar geometry to Fig. S7(i), but no IBC is used [Fig. S13(i)]. The initial thermal conductivity in the middle is 2κ . The full parameters are shown in Figs. S13(j)-S13(l). The temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s are presented in Figs. S13(m)-S13(o). The profile of Φ at a steady state is exhibited in Fig. S13(p), with a uniform gradient of Φ . Thermal radiation depicted by the Rosseland diffusion approximation

($\sim T^3$) is a particular case of nonlinear heat transfer. The diffusion invariant applies to general nonlinear heat transfer with arbitrary-form temperature dependence. As long as we set the same convective and radiative coefficients as thermal conductivity, the simultaneous manipulation of the three primary heat transfer modes can be implemented in principle.

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Table S1. Material parameters in Fig. S5(d).

Name	κ (W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ρC (10 ⁶ J m ⁻³ K ⁻¹)	ρC Ratio to GD-45
GD-450	2	3.5	1
HY-234	4	4.8	1.37
GD-31	1	4.48	1.28
HY-A9	11.4	5.55	1.59
HySal	0.37	3.5	1
HY-881	5.7	4.2	1.2
Asphalt	0.7	1.54	0.44
TC5628	3.6	4.5	1.29
GD-100	1.1	4	1.14
Graphite	400	1.61	0.46
VIP	0.01	0.045	0.013

HySal: Hydrated Salt

VIP: Vacuum Insulation Panel

FIG. S1. Spherical transient cloaking. (a) Thermal diffusivity D'/D via Eq. (S80). (b) Thermal conductivity κ'/κ via Eq. (S81). (c) Volumetric heat capacity $\rho'C'/\rho C$ via Eq. (S82). (d)-(f) 3D temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s. (g)-(i) Temperature profiles on the $z-x$ planes. (j)-(l) Temperature deviation evolutions at the circle, rhombus, and hexagon positions in (g)-(i). The inner and outer radii are $r_c = 0.2$ and $r_s = 0.4$ m.

FIG. S2. Temperature-diffusivity correlation. (a) Average temperature on the middle solid line $Ave(T)$ as a function of the reference thermal diffusivity D_T/D . (b) $Ave(T)$ as a function of the area fraction of brown particles p , with $\kappa_1/\kappa = 5$ and $\rho_1 C_1/\rho C = 0.2$. The blue matrix has parameters of $\kappa_2/\kappa = 1$ and $\rho_2 C_2/\rho C = 1$.

FIG. S3. Simulations of the samples. Temperature profiles of the (a)-(d) Bare, (e)-(h) Cloak, and (i)-(l) Reference cases at 15, 30, 60, and 120 mins.

FIG. S4. Ideal omnidirectional cloaking. (a)-(d) Unidirectional cloaking at 0° : (a) Thermal conductivity; (b) Volumetric heat capacity; (c) and (d) Temperature (T) profiles at 0.03 and 0.15 s. (e)-(h) As in (a)-(d), but at 90° . (i)-(p) Temperature profiles based on the parameters given by Eqs. (S83) and (S84). Omnidirectional cloaking can be observed at 30° , 60° , 0° , and 90° .

FIG. S5. Practical omnidirectional cloaking. (a) Layered thermal conductivity. (b) Practical volumetric heat capacity. (c) Coarse-grained volumetric heat capacity. (d) Practical structure. (e)-(l) Temperature (T) profiles at 40 and 140 mins at 0° , 30° , 60° , and 90° based on the parameters in (a) and (c). (m)-(t) As in (e)-(l), but based on the parameters in (d). The simulation size is $20 \times 20 \text{ cm}^2$.

FIG. S6. Circular transient concentrating-rotating. (a) Radial component of the ideal anisotropic thermal conductivity from Eq. (S85), with parameters of $m = 1.5$, $\theta_0 = \pi/6$, $r_c = 0.2$, and $r_s = 0.4$ m. (b) Volumetric heat capacity from Eqs. (S89) and (S91). (c) Thermal conductivity from Eqs. (S94a) and (94b). (d) Volumetric heat capacity. (e) and (f) Temperature profiles at 0.06 and 0.6 s with the parameters in (a) and (b). (g) and (h) Those with the parameters in (c) and (d). The arrows denote heat flux. (i)-(l) As in (e)-(h), but applying a vertical temperature gradient.

FIG. S7. Complex-shape transient cloaking. (a) The TBC and IBC generate an orthogonal mesh of isotherms and streamlines. (b) Thermal diffusivity D'/D . (c) Thermal conductivity κ'/κ . (d) Volumetric heat capacity $\rho'C'/\rho C$. (e)-(g) Temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s. (h) Temperature deviation (η) evolutions over time t . (i)-(p) As in (a)-(h), but in 3D.

FIG. S8. Designing parameters by the FBC. (a) The FBC and IBC yield an orthogonal mesh of streamlines and isotherms. (b) Thermal conductivity κ'/κ from Eq. (S96). (c) Volumetric heat capacity $\rho'C'/\rho C$ based on Eq. (S98). (d)-(f) Temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s. (g)-(i) Temperature deviation evolutions.

FIG. S9. Extremely low thermal conductivity. (a) Replacing the IBC with an inner shell with a thermal conductivity of $10^{-5}\kappa$. (b) Thermal conductivity κ'/κ . (c) Volumetric heat capacity $\rho'C'/\rho C$. (d)-(f) Temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s. (g)-(i) Temperature deviation evolutions. The two lines are very close to each other.

FIG. S10. Designing parameters by the CTBC. (a) Removing the IBC and utilizing the CTBC. (b) Thermal conductivity. (c) Volumetric heat capacity. (d)-(f) Temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s. (g) and (h) Temperature deviation evolutions. (i) Temperature evolution on the inner boundary for artificial temperature control.

FIG. S11. Extremely high thermal conductivity. (a) Supplementing an inner shell with thermal conductivity of $10^5\kappa$ to replace the CTBC. (b)-(f) Full parameters of the shell and inner object. (g)-(i) Temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s. (j)-(l) Temperature deviation evolutions.

FIG. S12. From quasi-cloaking to cloaking. (a) Adding another shell with thermal conductivity of $10^{-5}\kappa$. (b) and (c) Volumetric heat capacity of the inner shell and object. (d)-(f) Temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s. (g)-(i) Temperature deviation evolutions. The two lines are very close to each other.

FIG. S13. Complex-shape transient transparency. (a)-(h) Thermal conductive and convective transparency: (a) mesh; (b) thermal conductivity; (c) volumetric heat capacity; (d) convective coefficient μ'/μ ; (e)-(g) temperature profiles at 0.01, 0.06, and 0.6 s; (h) pressure profile (P). (i)-(p) As in (a)-(h), but for implementing thermal conductive and radiative transparency in 3D. (l) Radiative coefficient β'/β . (p) Scalar potential profile (Φ) at the steady state. Other parameters: $\gamma = 4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m}^2$, $\zeta = 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$, $\rho_f C_f = 0.1\rho C$, and $\beta = 10 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-4}$.